

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SOCIAL SPHERE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE TERRITORY OF SYRDARYA REGION

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Abstract. *It is clear to everyone that the further development of small business and entrepreneurship in terms of improving living conditions is the most optimal and effective methods. The attention paid to this area by the head of state indicates significant changes in each region. Large-scale work is also being carried out in the development of profitable business areas such as manufacturing, service, tourism, etc. As a result, employment is achieved, new jobs are created with the most efficient use of previously ownerless land plots.*

Keywords: *hub, tourism, social sphere, service, entrepreneurship, production, innovation, innovative medicine, “BGI Group”, epicenter, active tourism.*

On April 7 of 2023, during a visit to Syrdarya region in order to get better acquainted with the development of the regions and the life of the population, the president announced that the city of Gulistan will be transformed into the “innovative medical hub” of our country. This means that in the future, the Uzbekistan—China biotechnology cluster will be built in Syrdarya with an investment of 500 million US Dollars on an area of 150 hectares.

It serves as the only Hub not only for Central Asia, but also for the CIS and Caucasian countries. It follows from this that this great turn in the field of medicine is the impetus for the further development of tourism in Uzbekistan, namely in Syrdarya region, visit of the peoples of Central Asia and the Caucasus countries as medical tourism, further brings improvement of the territory. Services also introduce the further development of the social sphere here.

The cluster includes the Uzbek-Sino Biotechnology University, which is designed to train National Personnel and engage in scientific research, the innovation medical clinic, which uses the latest diagnostic treatments in the treatment of diseases, the Central Asian population, the Central Asian genome center, which specializes in the study of the genome of animals and plants in the region, the Genetic banks and data center, a cell therapy curing tumors and cancers.

In addition, an enterprise for the production of diagnostic equipment and special kits for laboratories, a center for the production of innovative vaccines, will be built on the territory. Separate enterprises produce probiotic biopreparations, monoclonal antibodies and other recombinant medicines. A diagnostic center is set up to identify genetic problems in newborns and pregnant women. Also, educational buildings, a modern campus, laboratories, a school of engineers will be opened for 10 thousand students.

It follows from these processes that we observe the development of several types of tourism simultaneously. Including active types of tourism: such as medical tourism, social tourism, youth and children’s tourism.

The creation of a new biotechnological hub will also open the way to many of the advanced areas that our scientists have dreamed before. In particular, the genome of the population of

Uzbekistan is described. In the digital format, unique genetic collections are created. A decrease in the birth rate of children with genetic defects and diseases is achieved. Treatment of oncological diseases in a completely new way is established through cell and immunotherapy. Issues of combating aging, prolonging human life are researched and the results are put into practice. In the field of pharmaceuticals, safe and effective drugs are produced, invented according to the results of the study of the protective system of bioorganisms. Similar new biotechnological products created in this cluster are exported at the first stage to the countries of Central Asia and the Caucasus. At the same time, the transfer of knowledge and technology with developed countries makes it possible to export our products to the near and far abroad.

It is no coincidence that the cluster is built precisely in cooperation with China. This country ranks second in the world after the United States in the last five years in the development of the field of Biotechnology.

At this point, it is natural for a reasonable question to arise as to why this large platform is being set up in Syrdarya. The fact is that in recent years, as a result of the granting of academic independence, Gulistan State University has developed rapidly. In particular, a school of biologists appeared there. A team with the potential to operate in different areas of the biotechnology sector has been formed. As a result of this, the cluster of biotechnologies, which will be organized in the innovation area of Syrdarya region, will become the “epicenter” of all innovative processes in the field. At the “Reception House” of the regional authorities, the minister of Higher Education, Science and innovation Ibrahim Abdurahmonov and the regional governor Akmaljon Makhmudaliev held a meeting with the chairman of the company “BGI Group”, which is engaged in research on the human genome in China, Van Jian and his team, who are currently in our country.

At the beginning of the conversation, Van Jian expressed deep gratitude for the sincere reception and separately noted that this visit to Syrdarya, organized, was making a great impression on the members of the delegation. At the end, the parties agreed on practical aspects of effective and constructive cooperation.

In order to ensure the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5326 “On additional organizational measures to create favorable conditions for the development of tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan” from February 3, 2018, as one of the most important factors of sustainable socio-economic development of the regions, the rapid development of domestic tourism. In this case, the further development of Sardoba, Khovos and Syrdarya river tourism zones in the territory of Syrdarya region, the service of the region and the increase in the number of species should not be left without attracting visitors to the medical hub, which will be organized at the same time.

Taking the opportunity, the construction of special tourist guides, mobile applications, convenient and free Internet access areas, repair of highways, small cafes will also not be unprofitable for the visiting population.

Each tourist is required to react and serve based on their age, race, nationality, language and religion, social background, and psychophysiological status. The reason is, it is necessary to stay away from the actions that contradict visitors’ own national views, to organize tour packages, taking into account their young physiologically general circumstances and their interests in this regard. To do this, special touristic services should be launched in the field. The use of special

distribution flares for tourists as well as mobile applications is considered one of the modern methods of advertising.

REFERENCES

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